

Maximizing agreement on diverse ontologies with "wisdom of crowds" relation classification

Abstract

Purpose - Ontologies are defined as consensual formal conceptualization of shared knowledge. However, the explicit overlap between diverse ontologies is usually very low since they are typically constructed by different experts. Hence, in this paper we suggest to exploit "wisdom of crowds" to assess the maximal potential for inter-ontology agreement on controversial domains.

Design/methodology/approach - We propose a scheme where independent ontology users can explicitly express their opinions on the specified set of ontologies. The collected user opinions are further employed as features for machine classification algorithm to distinguish between the consensual ontological relations and the controversial ones. In addition, we devised new evaluation methods to measure the reliability and accuracy of the presented scheme.

Findings - The accuracy of the relation classification (90%) and the reliability of user agreement annotations were quite high (over 90%). These results indicate a fair ability of the scheme to learn the maximal set of consensual relations out of the specified set of diverse ontologies.

Practical implications – A diversity of opinions expressed by different ontologies has to be resolved in order to digitize many domains of knowledge (e.g. cultural heritage, folklore, medicine, economy, religion, history, art). This work presents a methodology to formally represent this diverse knowledge in a rich semantic scheme where there is a need to distinguish between the commonly shared and the controversial relations.

Research Limitations – The datasets and the group of participants in our experiments were of limited size and thus the presented results are promising but cannot be generalized at this stage of research.

Originality/value - To the best of our knowledge this is a first proposal to consider crowd-based evaluation and classification of ontological relations to maximize the inter-ontology agreement.

Introduction

In the past decade ontologies have been widely employed as formal definition of domain vocabularies. Semantically rich and standardized vocabulary is a key to success of many semantic web applications and knowledge-sharing activities (Gruber, 1993), such as semantic information tagging, retrieval and document summarization. However, currently, for many domains there are multiple semantically diverse ontologies rather than one consensual vocabulary model. This is due to the fact that they are typically constructed by different experts who often possess distinct and even contrary viewpoints especially in cases of controversial domains. These domains include cultural heritage, economy, politics, history,

religion, art and even medicine. For instance, controversial statements such as, "God created Universe" and "Homeopathy cures asthma", cannot be objectively evaluated as correct or incorrect since they convey subjective opinions depending on one's personal beliefs or experience. Therefore, for these domains there cannot be one ground truth, a single set of correct facts or statements.

In this context, we would like to explore whether it is possible to establish the reliable "crowd truth" annotation for ontological statements as *consensual* or *controversial* rather than truthful or false. In other words, the goal is to identify the maximal subset of widely agreed statements, and distinguish them from those with low user agreement. The notion of "crowd truth" has been recently discussed in (Aroyo and Welty, 2013). They conclude that low agreement rates characterize ambiguous or vague statements. As opposed in our case of highly controversial domains, these are assumed to be divisive viewpoint statements.

The existing approaches for matching or unifying ontologies usually focus on mapping individual entities (concepts and properties) of one ontology to similar entities in the other one (Euzenat et al., 2013; Fluoris et al., 2008; Sarasua et al., 2012). However, the ability of these methods to amplify inter-ontology agreement is limited by the terminological and structural overlap between the ontologies, which is typically quite low (less than 30%) as shown in the previous studies (Maedche and Staab, 2002; Liu and Gruen, 2008).

An additional limitation of the entity-based matching techniques is that the domain semantic knowledge and diversity of opinions are mostly expressed by relations or axioms binding different ontological entities into statements of the form: (*concept1*, *property/relationship*, *concept2*). Furthermore, these relations represent the entity contexts, or a set of facts expressed by ontologies and thus reflect their semantic level which cannot be directly derived from comparing only their entities and taxonomic structures. It can be observed that concepts matching out of context might belong to opposed viewpoints when put into different contexts or statements, which might lead to ontological inconsistencies. For example, there is a concept *C* ("Prime Minister") which is one of the domain concepts of a property *P* ("supports") and concepts *D* ("Social protest") and *E* ("renewable energy research") are in the range of *P*. This still does not mean that there is a triple $T=(\text{"Prime Minister"}, \text{"supports"}, \text{"Social protest"})$ binding *C*, *P* and *D* (or some of these concepts' sub-concepts or instances) together, since *C* and *D* are not the only concepts in the domain and range of *P*. Hence, matching of isolated entities does not reflect the maximal potential for *semantic* similarity of ontologies unless all the direct and indirect *relations* linking these entities can be consistently matched as well.

Thus, as opposed to the existing approaches, in this study we focus on relation-level ontological agreement. Increasing this type of agreement considered as a more complicated and important task than entity-based agreement and matching (Visser et al., 1998), and which still requires a deeper level of analysis and exploration.

To overcome the data sparseness problem, i.e. the low overlap between ontological relations in diverse ontologies, we introduce a new collaborative scheme where independent subjects can explicitly express their opinions (agreement or disagreement) on the provided set of ontological relations. Then, the *exhaustive* inter-ontology agreement can be calculated based on the "crowd truth" votes rather than by counting the common relations in the original source ontologies. The underlying assumption is that if a relation appears in only one or part of the ontologies in the set, this does not necessarily mean it is wrong or controversial.

Thus, the primary research question of this article is whether the "wisdom of crowds" is an effective and reliable instrument for maximizing the inter-ontology agreement for controversial domains.

To answer this question we experimented with a set of 20 ontologies for the domain of the "Jewish Israeli tradition and society" which comprises cultural, religious and political aspects. The obtained results show that our approach maximizes the agreement level between diverse ontologies. This is since the proposed "wisdom of crowds" relation annotation approach is not limited by the amount of common entities or relations of the ontologies, unlike the state-of-the-art automated ontology matching techniques. We also found that aggregated collaborative annotations can serve as a quite accurate and reliable predictor of consensual vs. controversial relations when employed as features in machine classification. The important implication of these findings is construction of the maximal unified model of consensual relations out of the given ontologies. However, we note that the datasets and the group of participants in our experiments were of limited size and thus the presented results are promising but are not generalizable at this stage of research.

The rest of this article is organized as follows: in the next section we present the survey of the related literature, in section 3 our collaborative scheme for relation agreement annotation is introduced, section 4 describes the evaluation methodology of the proposed scheme, the experimental results are demonstrated in section 5, and section 6 summarizes the main contributions and future work.

Related Work

Standardization of domain vocabulary is a crucial task for semantic web services and applications. Numerous matching methods for increasing agreement between diverse ontologies were presented in the past decade. However, since ontology matching is defined as finding correspondences or semantic relationships between their entities (Euzenat et al., 2011), these methods are not applicable to matching relations.

Two main approaches can be determined: (1) automatic approaches for identifying matches between entities from distinct ontologies; (2) collaborative ontology construction and matching.

A wide variety of studies were conducted on applying the first approach, automatic entity-based ontology matching (Chaffee and Gauch, 2000; Euzenat and Shvaiko, 2007; Euzenat et al., 2011; Shvaiko and Euzenat, 2013). To further quantify the agreement achieved by these techniques, multiple measures were proposed based on the amount of matches between the ontologies' entities (Cheng et al., 2011; David and Euzenat, 2008; Farooq et al., 2010; Madhavan, et al., 2001; Ngan et al., 2009; Staab, 2011; Xu, et al., 2012; Akbari and Fathian, 2010; Alasoud et al., 2009; Pirro and Talia, 2008). The general approach of these works is identifying and counting pairs of similar concepts and/or matching taxonomic structures of these concepts in two ontologies. One of the most prominent measures representing this approach was proposed by Maedche and Staab (2002) to measure term similarity, concept similarity and relationship (property) similarity. Concept similarity is measured by comparing their hyponymy hierarchies and relationship similarity based on the number of similar concepts in their ranges and domains. Another method, presenting the Glue system, was proposed by (Op 't Land et al., 2009). This system finds the mappings between the ontologies' concepts, assuming that every node in the taxonomy tree has a match, and computes the joint probability distribution for every node. (Dieng and Hug, 1998) automatically generate a common ontology of several experts from their personal ontologies. They employ algorithms for matching synonyms, similar terms and topological structures. Some works propose

employing external information to the ontology. For instance, Mazuel and Sabouret (2008) report improved results for their property-based similarity measure using Wordnet (Fellbaum, 2008) part-of relationships. In (Ehrig et al., 2005) the authors incorporate concept usage in context in their similarity measure in addition to terminological and taxonomic similarity. They argue that semantically similar concepts are used in similar contexts and good measures need to consider semantics and not just structure of the ontologies. Finally, Euzenat and Valtchev (2003) classify the various existing measures into the following types: terminological (T) string-based matching and terminological with lexicons, i.e. considering synonym as equivalent and hyponyms as subsumed; internal structure comparison (I) - comparing the value range or cardinality of their attributes; external structure comparison (S) - comparing the location of the concept in the taxonomy; extensional comparison (E) - comparing the set of other entities that are attached to them (in general instances of classes); semantic comparison (M) - comparing the interpretations of the entities. In a similar spirit, a recent article by Scharffe et al. (2013) introduces *ontology alignment patterns* that summarize the terminological and structural matching approach for ontological entities such as concepts, properties and instances.

The second approach based on user collaboration was recently applied in (Sarasua et al., 2012) where microtask crowdsourcing was exploited for collaborative ontological concept matching. Likewise, the PROMPT system (Noy and Musen, 2003) is one of the most prominent tools for merging ontologies based on their similar concepts (classes). PROMPT identifies a number of ontology merging operations (e.g. merge classes/concepts, merge properties, merge bindings between a property and a class), a number of possible conflicts and finds possible solutions to these conflicts and displays them to the user. (Liu and Gruen, 2008) adopted the ontology similarity measures of (Maedche and Staab, 2002). They conducted a user study where three ontologies for a specific domain were developed dynamically in a three phase process by nine subjects. In their experiments the subjects had to continue constructing the ontology started by others, but no direct interaction between subjects was allowed. In contrast, in several works on collaborative ontology integration, such as (Heflin, 2001; Holsapple and Joshi, 2002; Karaparis, 2012) the participants went through an iterative process of disagreement revision and discussion until reaching full consensus.

As described above, numerous studies exist which compare and align pairs of individual entities of ontologies, while relation matching, i.e. matching of RDF-style triples: (*concept A*, *property/relationship*, *concept B*) (including non-taxonomic relationship types), seems to be underexplored in the literature. Note that neither the automated matching patterns nor the collaborative methods described above apply to relations. Nevertheless, as explained in the previous section, the domain knowledge is mostly reflected by ontological relations linking the entities into statements. Thus, to capture the maximal potential agreement on ontologies the sets of their relations should be considered for matching and agreement. A first step towards this goal was implemented by d'Aquin (2009) who proposed an agreement and disagreement measures which calculate the exact or partial terminological matches (same terms but different relationship type) between RDF-style triples, i.e. relation-based matching. We believe that this line of research should be further developed to identify semantic matches and mismatches (inconsistencies) between relations, rather than direct terminological and structural correspondences between isolated entities, which we intend to accomplish in the current research.

In addition, all the above studies (including (d'Aquin, 2009) and the collaborative approaches) only consider the entities and relations explicitly inserted/occurring into the ontologies for

their comparison and agreement level calculation. In other words, if an entity or a relation is present in the first ontology but it is missing in the other, it will be handled as unmatched and disagreed. As opposed, in this work we suggest to facilitate the user collaboration for detection of implicitly consensual "crowd truth" relations independently of their occurrence frequency in the specified set of ontologies. The new approach for increasing the inter-ontology agreement is introduced in the next section.

Collaborative Scheme for Agreement Annotation of Ontological Relations

In this study we define an ontology as a set of axioms or relations of the form: (*concept1*, *property/relationship*, *concept2*). Note that this definition of ontology is language-independent as any formal ontology can be converted into such a triple-style representation. To measure the semantic agreement between diverse ontologies, we employ "wisdom of crowds" to annotate their relations. The goal of this annotation is to separate the consensual relations from the rest. To this end, we propose a new type of classification of ontological relations into three categories: 1) consensual - "crowd truth" statement agreed by the vast majority of subjects, 2) controversial – viewpoint statement agreed and disagreed by approximately similar amounts subjects, 3) and erroneous – statements disagreed by the majority of the subjects.

More formally, given a set of N diverse ontologies on the specified domain, we suggest to logically represent them as vectors of the size M , where M is the overall number of distinct relations they contain altogether. The values in the vectors will be $\{0,1\}$, such that a cell $V_{j,i}$ in the vector corresponding to ontology O_j and relation R_i contains 1, if R_i presents in O_j and 0 otherwise. Apparently, since the overlap between ontologies is very low, these vectors will be mostly consisted of "0" values. To complete the missing information, we introduce a collaborative scheme for agreement annotation of ontological relations.

At the basic level of the scheme for each relation, the subjects were asked whether they agree or disagree with the truth of the relation statement at least in some contexts of the domain. Nevertheless, in controversial domains participants tend to assign disagreement votes not only to relations that are objectively erroneous but rather since they do not fit their own beliefs and worldview. Therefore, to investigate the reasons for disagreement and better capture the differences between relation types we further refined the above binary scheme. Consequently, the following exclusive sub-categories were added to the collaborative scheme to supply possible reasons for their disagreements:

(1) **No Relation (NR)** - Disagree because the correct relation between two classes (in the statement) should be unrelated, e.g. (*God, creates, Universe*) - from the atheist's perspective the two concepts are unrelated;

(2) **Contradictory Relation (CR)** – Disagree since the concepts are related but the relationship type between these concepts should be semantically inverse, opposite or contradictory to the given one (*Reform Jew – is-a / disjoint-with – Orthodox Jew; Land of Israel – part-of/includes – Country of Israel; Orthodox Jew - resist / contribute – Scientific progress; God - similar / opposite-to – Man*);

(3) **Entailing Relation (ER)** – Disagree because the relationship type should be different, neither contradictory nor unrelated, but rather compatible and semantically entailing of the assigned one (*Passover – is-a / instance-of – Jewish Holiday; Orthodox Jew – contribute /*

part-of – *Israeli Society*). IS-A and instance-of relationships are mutually substitutable in this case, while "contribute" is a sub-relationship of "part-of" and semantically entails its meaning.

(4) **Wrong Relation (WR)** – Disagree since the statement includes an ontological or factual error that cannot be resolved by one of the above options (e.g. *Prayer - instance-of - Synagogue* (instead of "takes_place"); *Woman – instance-of – Status of women* (instead of "affected by")), or objectively incorrect concepts (e.g. *David's Tower – located-at – City of Hebron* (instead of Jerusalem));

Note that subjects could choose only one of the above sub-categories for a given relation. These sub-categories can be also viewed as alternative relations that, on the annotator's opinion, could substitute the given ones. In the next section we further analyze the histograms of each sub-category for different types of relations and investigate their influence on the relation classification.

The objectively truthful relations, like, (Passover, IS-A, Jewish holiday); (Reform Jew, disjoint-with, Orthodox Jew); (Western Wall, located-at, Jerusalem) are expected to obtain the large majority of agreement votes in the collaborative annotation procedure, while the controversial relations such as, (Orthodox Jew, resists, Scientific progress); (Bible, written by, Man); (God, opposite-to, Man) are supposed to gain intermediate scores for both agreement and disagreement voting subcategories. A high voting rates for subcategories 1 (NR) and 2 (CR) are anticipated to reflect controversial viewpoint relations, subcategory 4 (WR) points out to the erroneous relations, while subcategory 3 (ER) might be referred as "weak agreements". Relations with a high level of weak and full agreement are hypothetically consensual relations. In summary, we hypothesize the introduced annotation subcategories are designed to be indicative of the consensus/controversy level of the relations.

A long-term implication of the above scheme lies in the field of ontology unification into one standard vocabulary. To this end, erroneous relations should be eliminated from the final unified ontology. Relations with a high level of weak and/or full agreement comprising similar classes and distinct inter-relationships constitute a match and can be represented by a single relation in the integrated ontology. Also, the above sub-categories can be used to diversify the unified ontology and generate the alternative corresponding relations. For example, if some of the source ontologies include a relation (Orthodox Jew, resist/disjoint-with Israeli society) and there was a significant amount of votes of subcategory 2 for this relation, then a relation with an opposed relationship type (Orthodox Jew, contribute to/part-of, Israeli society) can be added to the unified ontology.

Methods

Experimental setting

Based on the above collaborative scheme for relation annotation we conducted an experiment with 20 subjects (students of the Semantic web course in the Information Science Department who have taken 4-hours training in ontology engineering). We made sure that the 20 participants of our experiments belong to quite heterogeneous groups of the society and not biased toward a certain religious or political viewpoint. In particular, a 20% of them were observant, another 40% secular and the rest traditional and 40% of them voted for right-wing parties in the last elections, roughly 30% for the center-wing parties and approximately 30% for the left-wing parties.

The process consisted of two main steps.

Step I: Every subject was required to construct up to 100 RDF-style ontological triples (relations) with the above concepts and a set of 15 predefined relationships (such as, IS-A, instance-of, part-of, includes, unrelated, opposed-to, disjoint-with, entails, located-at) independently from the other subjects. The produced ontology's relations were inserted into the web-based system implemented for this purpose. As a result 20 personal ontologies were generated, which overall included 1175 distinct ontological relations. Note that the chosen domain is considered quite controversial and so the ontologies constructed by composers who possess different viewpoints on the subject were supposed to reflect this diversity of opinions.

Step II: At the second step, each one of 1175 relations, created at the former step, was consecutively displayed by the system and independently evaluated by each one of the subjects. The relation triple was converted into the corresponding statement and displayed to the subjects with the above 5 categories of agreement/disagreement to select from. The subjects had to assign the most appropriate type (amongst the five disagreement types in our scheme) for each statement.

The entire process of ontology construction and agreement annotation took 4-5 hours per subject. Note that the first step of constructing personal ontologies was unavoidable to assess the potential maximal inter-ontology agreement in the worst case. This is since there is no available set of over a dozen viewpoint ontologies on a controversial domain suited for our specific experimental goals.

Evaluation of the reliability of the proposed collaborative scheme

Recently, a group of researchers conducted a series of experiments on verification of ontology's taxonomic relations (subclassOf, IS-A) by microtask crowdsourcing (Noy et al, 2013; Mortensen et al., 2013). They asked the participants at the Amazon Mechanical Turk crowdsourcing platform to answer simple true/false questions formulated for the taxonomic relations from a few existing ontologies in the biomedical domain, such as "Is Heart always an Organ". Their goal was to compare the relations judged as true by the turkers to the "ground truth" relations from the ontology constructed by experts. The researchers reported quite high levels of average precision (88%) compared to the ground truth ontology. However, their methodology cannot be employed in the case of controversial domains when there is no ground truth ontology.

Therefore, a new reliability evaluation approach for "wisdom of crowds" agreement annotation of ontological relations is to be devised. Thus, we suggest that the reliability of the proposed annotation scheme can be tested by comparing the resulting classification of semantically equivalent or similar relations. In general, we assume that relations similar in meaning belong to similar agreement classes: either they are both consensual or not. On the other hand, the situation, when a relation was annotated as consensual, but the other semantically similar relation was annotated as viewpoint or erroneous, points to inconsistency in the annotation. In this regards, three groups of partially terminologically matching relations were compared:

1. Identical relations except for one concept in relations *R1* that is a subclass (hyponym) or an instance of the parallel concept in the relation *R2*.
2. Relations with identical concepts but different relationship types.
3. Relations with identical but switched concepts.

However, not all the relations in the above groups are automatically considered as similar. Hence, for each of the above group a sub-group of semantically similar relations are extracted according to the following restraints:

- Group 1 semantically similar subgroup: According to the ontological inference rules (Hayes and McBride, 2004) the super class-concept inherits all its properties and relationship types to its subclasses. Therefore, for group 1, if $R2$ (the super class concept relation) is classified as 1 then $R1$ (the subclass concept relation) is expected to be 1 as well and if $R2$ is 0 then so is $R1$. For example, (Passover, IS-A, Jewish Holiday) vs. (Passover, IS-A, Holiday), where Jewish Holiday is a subclass of Holiday.
- Group 2 semantically similar subgroup: The two relations are supposed to be identically classified when the relationships are semantically similar or related according to the textual or lexical entailment definition (Dagan et al., 2009; Geffet and Dagan, 2005), e.g. (Progress, entailed by, Education) vs. (Progress, caused-by, Education), (Kippah (skull cap), IS-A, Jewish tradition) vs. (Kippah, part-of, Jewish tradition). The types of such relationships are summarized in Table 1.
- Group 3 semantically similar subgroup: We expect similar classification in cases of semantically similar or inverse relationships, e.g. (Pitta Bread, disjoint-with, Passover) vs. (Passover, unrelated, Pitta Bread), (Western Wall, part-of, Holy Place) vs. (Holy Place, includes, Western Wall). Table 2 presents the types of semantic relationships that are included in this group.

Table 1: The golden standard similar pairs of relations of Group 1 (identical concepts but different relationships).

1 st relationship type	relation	2 nd relationship type	relation	Examples
IS-A, OF, ENTAILS	INSTANCE- PART-OF, ENTAILS	IS-A, OF, ENTAILS	INSTANCE- PART-OF, ENTAILS	(Western Wall, instance-of, Holy Place) vs. (Western Wall, IS-A, Holy Place), vs. (Western Wall, part-of, Holy Place) vs. (Western Wall, entails, Holy Place)
PART-OF		LOCATED-AT		(Western Wall, located-at, Holy Place) vs. (Western Wall, part-of, Holy Place)
UNRELATED		DISJOINT-WITH		(Democratic country, unrelated, Halakha religious law country) vs. (Democratic country, disjoint-with, Halakha religious law country)
CAUSES		ENTAILS		(Education, causes, Progress) vs. (Education, entails, Progress)

Table 2: The golden standard similar pairs of relations of Group 2 (identical but switched concepts).

1 st relationship type	relation	2 nd relationship type	relation	Examples
INCLUDES		PART-OF, LOCATED-AT		(Western Wall, part-of, Jerusalem) vs. (Jerusalem, includes, Western Wall) vs.

		(Western Wall, located-at, Jerusalem)
OPPOSED-TO	OPPOSED-TO	(Orthodox Jew, opposed-to, atheist) vs. (atheist, opposed-to, Orthodox Jew)
DISJOINT-WITH, UNRELATED	DISJOINT-WITH, UNRELATED	(Pitta Bread, unrelated, Passover) vs. (Passover, unrelated, Pitta Bread)
CAUSES, ENTAILS	CAUSED-BY, ENTAILED-BY	(Education, causes, Progress) vs. (Progress, entailed-by, Education)
SUPPORTS	SUPPORTED-BY	(Israeli society, supports, Orthodox Jew) vs. (Orthodox Jew, supported-by, Israeli society)
IS-A/INSTANCE- OF/PART- OF/ENTAILS	ENTAILED-BY	(Maimonides, instance-of, Rabbi) vs. (Maimonides, entails, Rabbi) vs. (Rabbi, entailed-by, Maimonides).

The subgroups of relation pairs above constitute "the golden standard" semantically similar relations anticipated to belong to similar agreement classes. Therefore, to assess the reliability level of the proposed agreement annotation we retrieved all the pairs of relations from our set of relations (1175) which belong to one of the three groups above. 383 pairs of relations were extracted for group 1, 420 pairs for group 2 and 505 pairs for group 3. Further, for every group, the golden standard annotation of pairs of relations was automatically derived from their relationships' semantics as shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Finally, we measure the relative recall of the agreement annotation scheme compared to the golden standard above, as follows: how many of the semantically equivalent relations according to the golden standard were classified to similar agreement classes by the aggregated subject annotations.

Effectiveness evaluation of the proposed collaborative scheme

Once collected the subjects' annotations are aggregated as "wisdom of crowds" to maximize the inter-ontology agreement. Consequently, to assess the effectiveness of the proposed scheme we measure the increase in pairwise agreement for every pair of ontologies in the above set of 20 personal ontologies. Additionally, we estimate the global agreement for all the ontologies in this set. To this end, we calculate the maximal subset of consensual ("crowd truth") relations out of all 1175 relations in our ontologies.

Contribution to the pairwise agreement maximization

First, the baseline and the collaborative agreements between all pairs of ontologies in the set were calculated. We computed two types of baseline agreement. The first baseline agreement is the relative amount of the common relations that appear in the two ontologies. The second baseline considers pairs of relations that are terminologically different but semantically similar according to the types of relationships presented in Tables 1 and 2 above. The exhaustive collaborative agreement is a relative amount of relations which either appear in both ontologies or appear in one of them and are annotated as fully agreed or entailing by the subject who is a composer of the second ontology. To calculate each of the agreement types, d'Aquin's (2009) ontology agreement measure was applied:

$$agreement(O_1, O_2) = \frac{\sum_{st \in ST_1} agreement(st, O_2) + \sum_{st \in ST_2} agreement(st, O_1)}{|ST_1| + |ST_2|}$$

Next, we compare the obtained baseline scores to those of the exhaustive collaborative agreement rates for all the pairs of ontologies in the set.

Global agreement evaluation

As a second step in effectiveness evaluation we estimate the accuracy of prediction of "crowd truth" relations by employing the above agreement annotations. We hypothesize that subject agreement will be high for consensual relations, low for erroneous relations and equally intermediate agreement and disagreement rates will be assigned to viewpoint relations.

One of the criteria for successful exploitation of "wisdom of crowds" is the aggregation function that sums up the individual subjects' votes and turns them into a collective decision (Surowiecki, 2005). To this end, instead of experimentally devising some heuristics (like in d'Aquin (2009)), we apply a well-grounded machine classification algorithm to calculate the *global agreement* on a set of ontologies. The global agreement is defined as the size of the maximal subset of relations from different ontologies that are consensual, i.e. agreed by the majority of the subjects. To compute the global agreement between the ontologies in the set, the number of subjects' annotations for each relation and every sub-category of agreement/disagreement was summed up. Then, for every ontological relation, a feature vector was constructed comprising 5 features of cumulative agreement/disagreement votes. For example, for a given relation: (Passover, IS-A, Jewish Holiday) assuming that 15 subjects agreed with it, 1 disagreed for subcategory NR, 1 disagreed for CR, 3 disagreed for ER, and none disagreed for WR, then the respective values will appear in its vector: $(15, 1, 1, 3, 0)$.

The resulting vectors were further employed to automatically learn the optimal machine classifier that discriminates the consensual relations from the rest. The aim of this classifier is to predict automatically the most matching class: 1) consensual relations denoted as 'C'; 2) controversial viewpoint relations ('V'); or 3) erroneous relations, 'E', for a given relation. To this end, we conducted a series of experiments with a widely used WEKA environment (Hall et al., 2009), where numerous supervised classification algorithms were applied on the set of the above ontological statements. The results elicited by various algorithms were evaluated by 10-fold cross validation method.

Note that supervised machine classification techniques are based on the expert "golden standard" annotation. Thus, in our case, the ontological relations are to be manually classified by experts as 'C', 'V' or 'E'. Then, roughly speaking, for each class ('C', 'V' or 'E') the algorithm learns its "profile model". Further, to classify a new unannotated relation the learnt classifier compares the values in its feature vectors to the characterizing model of each class and finds the best match.

Hence, a golden standard annotation required by supervised classification was performed as follows. Two experts (with polar viewpoints on the domain) were asked to annotate all the relations as one of the classes above: consensual relations ('C'), viewpoint relations ('V') or erroneous relations ('E'). First, the experts worked independently and then discussed and revised each other's choices to reach full consensus. Overall, 885 (out of 1175) relations were

judged as consensual, 231 as viewpoint and 59 as erroneous. Some examples are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Examples of consensual, viewpoint and erroneous relations.

Consensual relations	Viewpoint relations	Erroneous relations
Passover, instance-of, Jewish Holiday	God, part-of vs. unrelated, Universe	Women status, instance-of, Woman
Shabbat, is-a, Rest	Bicycle, part-of vs. unrelated, Yom Kippur ¹	Reform Jew, IS-A, Orthodox Jew
Kippah, part-of, Jewish tradition	Passover, includes vs. unrelated, Pitta Bread	Multi-child family, instance-of, Orthodox Jew
Israeli music, part-of, Jewish music	Joy, disjoint-with vs. part-of, poverty	Land of Israel, caused-by, settlers
Rabbi, IS-A, Jew	Orthodox Jew, part-of vs. disjoint-with, Israeli society	Faith, instance-of, Person

Finally, the higher the number of correctly (compared to expert annotation) classified relations by the classifier is, the higher is the accuracy and the effectiveness of the proposed collaborative scheme for global agreement on the set of diverse ontologies. It should be emphasized that our experts do not construct a golden standard ontology comprising ground truth relations as such an ontology cannot be created due to the controversy of the domain. Neither do they decide whether a relation is correct or not. In contrast, they only annotate the relations in the given ontologies as consensual, viewpoint or erroneous to provide a baseline for comparison to the corresponding "wisdom of crowds" classification.

Results and discussion

Contribution to pairwise agreement

The analysis of the results shows that the initial explicit agreement between the diverse ontologies was very low (0-22%) reflecting the controversy of the domain. The exhaustive pairwise inter-ontology agreement assessed by applying the collaborative evaluation procedure appears to be much higher (60-98%), as demonstrated in Figure 1. Thus, our collaborative scheme substantially enhances (by over 60%, 7% and 22% vs. 85% on average) both baselines' agreement level. Note that the second baseline imitates the optimal results of semantic relation matching to reach the top possible explicit agreement rates. Yet, they are significantly lower than the results of "wisdom of crowds"-based agreement.

¹Since there are no cars on the roads on this day, the tradition of non-observant Jews on Yom Kippur (The Trial day) is riding the bicycle, while it is forbidden by the religious law.

Contribution to the global agreement

Global agreement aims to identify the maximal subset of consensual "crowd truth" relations from all the ontologies in the set. For the baseline, at the global level, no relation was explicitly common for all or for the majority (11 out of 20) ontologies in our set. Hence, the explicit global agreement for the constructed ontologies at the step I of the experiment is 0.

There was only one relation common for 9 ontologies (Rabbi Ovadia Yosef, instance-of, Orthodox Jew), 8 relations were common for 7 ontologies (Secular Jew, opposed to, Orthodox Jew), (Woman, IS-A, Person), (Man, IS-A, Person), (Passover, instance-of, Jewish Holiday), (Siren, part-of, Memorial Day), (Rabbi, part-of, Rabbinite), (Shema Israel, instance-of, Prayer), (Shemona Esrei, instance-of, Prayer), while most of the relations (almost 80%, 927 out of 1175) appeared in only one ontology as demonstrated by Figure 2.

The analysis of the collaborative annotation data shows that for 99% (877 out of 885) of the relations annotated as 'C' (consensual) by the golden standard, there was an over 70% agreement (full or weak) among the subjects, while for 92% of the erroneous relations over 50% (the majority) of the subjects clearly disagreed (with types of 'NR', 'WR' or 'CR').

We further explore whether the different types of agreement and disagreement annotations reflect different relation classes. To this end, we created the histograms for every annotation type to compare the amounts of relations of each class for different numbers of votes. The elicited results are displayed in Figure 3. It can be viewed that high ranges of ER (entailing relationship) and full agreement are representative of consensual relations, while CR (contradictory relationship) is characteristic of viewpoint ones, WR (wrong relationship) as expected is indicative of the erroneous relations when the number of votes is 5 and above, while NR (no relation) is equally high for viewpoint and erroneous relations and low for consensual relations.

Numerous supervised classification algorithms from the WEKA system were applied on the set of the above ontological relations to calculate the global agreement rates. Eventually, the best 10-cross validation results, achieved by the Multilayer Perceptron algorithm (related to the later state-of-the-art SVM algorithm), are demonstrated in Figure 4. Note that the classic SVM algorithm elicited close but slightly worse results. The displayed graph includes the results for four classification experiments: (1) 3-class classification (86% accuracy); (2) binary classification discriminating the consensual relations (class 'C') from all the rest (the union of classes 'V' and 'E' as a second class) (90% accuracy); (3) binary classification distinguishing between the consensual and viewpoint relations (classes of 'C' and 'V'

correspondingly) with 89% accuracy; (4) binary classification of viewpoint vs. erroneous relations (84% accuracy).

We also experimented with more generalized feature vectors, e.g. two feature vectors comprised one feature for agreement (summing up entailing annotation type, ER, with the full agreement votes) and the other for disagreement (summing up NR, WR and CR votes). But the obtained results were slightly worse than for the original 5-feature vectors (81% instead of 84% accuracy for 3-class classification experiment), which means that each feature contributes some unique information and improves the classification accuracy.

The Reliability Level of "Wisdom of crowds" Ontological Relation Annotations

To assess the reliability and consistency of the proposed annotation scheme we analyzed the classifications of semantically similar relations divided into three groups as described in previous section. Apparently, it is expected that such relations will be identically classified by our "wisdom of crowds" based classifier. Table 4 presents the obtained results. Column 2 shows the overall number of partially terminologically similar relations in the groups. Column 3 demonstrates the subgroups of relations that conform to the semantic similarity constraints for each group. The amount and percentage of relations identically classified out of all the semantically similar relations (in Column 3) are exhibited in Columns 4 and 5, respectively.

The overall average percentage of identically classified pairs of semantically similar relations for all groups is 92.5%. This finding leads to the conclusion that the "wisdom of crowds" annotation of our subjects as a group was quite reliable.

Table 4: Annotation Consistency Test Results. The recall values for the semantically similar relations classified to the same classes by the automated classifier based on the agreement annotation votes.

	Number of terminologically matching relation pairs in the group	Number of semantically similar pairs of relations by golden standard subgroup	Number of identically classified pairs of relations	Percent of identically classified pairs of relations
Group 1: superclass-subclass relations	383	359	323	89.9
Group 2: identical concepts different relationships	420	286	271	94.8
Group 3: switched concepts	505	351	327	93.2
Total	1308	996	921	92.5

Conclusions

Ontology construction and evaluation are tasks that require human assistance (Sarasua et al., 2012). Hence, in this study we propose to employ "wisdom of crowds" for maximizing the relation-based inter-ontology agreement.

Following are the main contributions of this work:

- 1) A new approach to *semantic* ontology agreement evaluation was proposed based on relations rather than on individual entities in the ontologies.
- 2) A new collaborative scheme for *exhaustive* agreement annotation of ontological relations was developed. This scheme overcomes the problem of low overlap in diverse ontologies and thus unveils the "hidden" implicit inter-ontology agreement. In our experiments the subjects were requested to explicitly evaluate their agreement with relations in others' ontologies.
- 3) Since no ground truth ontology exists for controversial domains, we define a notion of "crowd truth" for ontological relations that are consensual according to the "wisdom of crowds" agreement annotations as opposed to controversial relations.
- 4) Based on the presented annotation scheme we proposed a new evaluation methodology for computing the pairwise and global agreement for a given set of ontologies. Instead of the traditional comparison to the ground truth, the objective of measuring global agreement is to distinguish the consensual "crowd truth" relations from the viewpoint and erroneous ones. Consequently, a maximal subset of consensual vocabulary for the controversial domain can be constructed. The subjects' agreement annotations were exploited as features for learning the optimal classifier for this purpose. From the analysis of 20 personal ontologies on the Jewish tradition and society domain we found that the actual user agreement on ontologies at the relation level is much higher than the baseline. Thus, the majority of the relations were commonly accepted and regarded as consensual despite the fact that they

initially appeared in only one or two out of the 20 ontologies. Therefore, we conclude that "wisdom of crowds" can boost the inter-ontology agreement level.

- 5) In addition, a new method for assessment of agreement annotation reliability was devised. The collected annotations were found quite consistent in cases of semantically similar relations.

In summary, the result of the proposed approach is a set of ontological relations from diverse ontologies classified with 90% accuracy as consensual, controversial viewpoint or erroneous. Further, all the consensual relations could be automatically or semi-automatically merged into a consistent unified ontological model. Thus, our method provides a basis for collaborative ontology unification.

In addition, our results show that the "wisdom of crowds" annotation significantly increases the baseline agreement that can be achieved manually or automatically from the explicitly overlapping, terminologically or semantically similar relations.

The limitation of the current research is that it examines a number of personal ontologies created and evaluated by our subjects rather than by wide crowds. Therefore, in future work, we intend to apply the proposed classification scheme in experiments based on the microtask crowdsourcing methodology. As a long-term research goal, a unified multi-viewpoint ontology (Djakhadjakha et al., 2012) will be created based on the proposed agreement annotation scheme. This ontology will integrate the consensual relations from different personal ontologies along with the controversial viewpoints thus reflecting the diversity of opinions on the domain. Hence, based on the provided methodology for ontological relation classification a new approach for effective ontology unification can be developed allowing for multiple controversial viewpoints to co-exist in the unified model.

References

- Akbari, I. and M. Fathian (2010), A novel algorithm for ontology matching, *Journal of Information Science*, Vol. 36, pp. 324-334.
- Alasoud, A., Haarslev, V. and N, Shiri (2009), An empirical comparison of ontology matching techniques, *Journal of Information Science*, Vol. 35, pp. 379-397.
- An, J., D. Quercia and J. Crowcroft (2013), Why individuals seek diverse opinions (or why they don't), In *Proceedings of the Web Science 2013 Conference*, Paris.
- Aroyo, L. and C. Welty (2013), Crowd Truth: Harnessing disagreement in crowdsourcing a relation extraction gold standard, In *Proceedings of the Web Science 2013 Conference*, Paris.
- Chaffee, J, and S. Gauch (2000), Personal ontologies for web navigation, In *Proceedings of the Ninth International Conference on Information and knowledge management*, McLean, VA, pp. 227-234.
- Cheng, G., Gong, S., and Y. Qu (2011), An empirical study of vocabulary relatedness and its application to recommender systems, In *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on the Semantic Web*, Koblenz, Germany, pp. 98-113.

David, J., and J. Euzenat (2008), Comparison between ontology distances (preliminary results), In *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on the Semantic Web*, Karlsruhe, Germany, pp. 245-260.

d'Aquin, M. (2009), Formally measuring agreement and disagreement in ontologies. In *Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Knowledge Capture*, Redondo Beach, California, USA, pp. 145-152.

deBruijn, J., Ehrig, M., Feier, C., Martin-Recuerda, F., Scharffe, F., and M. Weiten (2006), Ontology mediation, merging and aligning. In: Davies, J., Studer, R., Warren, P. (eds.), *Semantic Web Technologies: Trends and Research in Ontology-Based Systems*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons Ltd., pp. 95-114.

Dieng, R., and S. Hug (1998), Comparison of "personal ontologies" represented through conceptual graphs, In *Proceedings of the 13th European Conference on Artificial Intelligence (ECAI 98)*, Brighton, UK, pp. 341-345.

Djakhdjakha, L., Hemam M., and Z. Boufaida (2012), Multi-viewpoints ontology alignment based on Description Logics, *Communications in Computer and Information Science*, Vol. 294, pp. 109-122.

Euzenat, J., Meilicke, C., Shvaiko, P., Stuckenschmidt, H. and C. Trojahn dos Santos (2011), Ontology alignment evaluation initiative: Six years of experience. *Journal of Data Semantics*, Vol. 15, pp. 158-192.

Euzenat, J., and P. Shvaiko (2007), *Ontology matching*, Heidelberg, Germany: Springer.

Euzenat, J., and P. Valtchev (2003), An integrative proximity measure for ontology alignment, In *Proceedings of ISWC-2003 workshop on semantic information integration*, Sanibel Island (FL US), pp. 33-38.

Ehrig, M., Haase, P., Hefke, M., and N. Stojanovic (2005), Similarity for ontologies – a comprehensive framework, In *Proceedings of the 13th European Conference on Information Systems, Information Systems in a Rapidly Changing Economy (ECIS)*, Regensburg, Germany, pp. 13-24.

Farooq, A., Ahsan, S. and A. Shah (2010), An efficient technique for similarity identification between ontologies, *Journal of Computing*, Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 147-155.

Fahad, M., Moalla, N. and A. Bouras (2012), Detection and resolution of semantic inconsistency and redundancy in an automatic ontology merging system, *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*, Vol. 39 No. 2, pp. 535-557.

Fellbaum, C. (1998), *WordNet: An electronic lexical database*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.

Flouris G., Manakanatas D., Kondylakis H., Plexousakis D. and G. Antoniou. (2008), Ontology change: classification and survey, *The Knowledge Engineering Review*, Vol. 23 No. 2, pp. 117–152.

- Geffet, M. and I. Dagan (2004), Distributional inclusion hypotheses and lexical entailment. *Proceedings of the 43rd Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL)*, Ann Arbor, Michigan, pp. 107-114.
- Hall, M., Frank, E., Holmes, G., Pfahringer, B., Reutemann, P., I. H. Witten (2009), The WEKA data mining software: an update. *SIGKDD Explorations*, Vol. 11 No. 1, pp. 10-18.
- Hayes, P. and B. McBride (last accessed July 2013), RDF Semantics, W3C Recommendation: <http://www.w3.org/TR/2004/REC-rdf-mt-20040210/> (2004 last accessed July 2013).
- Heflin, J. (2001), *Towards the Semantic web: Knowledge representation in a dynamic, distributed environment*, Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Maryland, College Park.
- Holsapple, C. W. and Joshi, K. D. (2002), Ontology applications and design: A collaborative approach to ontology design. *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 45 No. 2, pp. 42-47.
- Liu, J., and D.M. Gruen (2008), Between ontology and folksonomy: A study of collaborative and implicit ontology evolution, In *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Intelligent User Interfaces*, ACM, Gran Canaria, Canary Islands, Spain, pp. 361-364.
- Madhavan, J., Bernstein, P. A., and E. Rahm (2001), Generic schema matching with cupid. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Very Large Data Bases*, Rome, Italy, pp. 49-58.
- Maedche, A., and S. Staab (2002), Measuring similarity between ontologies, In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Knowledge Engineering and Knowledge Management. Ontologies and the Semantic Web*, Sigüenza, Spain, pp. 15-21.
- Mazuel, L., and N. Sabouret (2008), Semantic relatedness measure using object properties in an ontology, In *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on the Semantic Web*, Karlsruhe, Germany, pp. 681-694.
- Mortensen, J. M., Musen, M. A., and N. F. Noy (2013), Crowdsourcing the Verification of Relationships in Biomedical Ontologies, *AMIA 2013 Annual Symposium*.
- Ngan, L.D., Goh, A.E.S., and L.Q. Hung (2009), Comparing two ontologies, *International Journal of Web Engineering and Technology*, Vol. 5 No. 1, pp. 48-68.
- Noy, N.F. and Musen, M.A. (2003), The PROMPT suite: interactive tools for ontology merging and mapping, *International Journal of Human Computer Studies*, Vol. 59 No. 6, pp. 983-1024.
- Noy, N. F., Mortensen, J. M., Alexander, P. R., and M. A. Musen (2013), Mechanical Turk as an Ontology Engineer? Using Microtasks as a Component of an Ontology-Engineering Workflow, In *Proceedings of the Web Science 2013 Conference*, Paris.

Op 't Land M., Zwitser H., Ensink P. and Lebel, Q (2009), Towards a fast enterprise ontology based method for post merger integration, In *Proceedings of the 2009 ACM Symposium on Applied Computing*, Honolulu, HI, USA, pp. 245–52.

Pirro, G. and D. Talia (2008), LOM: a linguistic ontology matcher based on information retrieval, *Journal of Information Science*, Vol. 34 No. 6, pp. 845–860.

Sarasua, C., Simperl, E. and N.F. Noy (2012), Crowdmap: Crowdsourcing ontology alignment with microtasks, In *Proceedings of the International Semantic Web Conference*, Boston, USA, pp. 525- 541.

Scharffe, F., Zamazal, O. and D.Fensel (2013), Ontology alignment design patterns, *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 00:1-00 (last accessed August 2013).

Shvaiko P. and J. Euzenat (2013), Ontology matching: state of the art and future challenges. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*.

Staab, S (2011), Ontologies and similarity, In *Proceedings of the 19th international conference on Case-Based Reasoning Research and Development*, London, UK, pp. 11-16.

Surowiecki, J. (2005), *The wisdom of crowds*. New York: Doubleday.

Visser, P.R.S., D.M. Jones, T.J.M. Bench-Capon and M.J.R. Shave (1998), Assessing heterogeneity by classifying ontology mismatches, In N. Guarino (ed.) *Formal Ontology in Information Systems*, IOS Press, Amsterdam, pp.148-162.

Xie, J., Liu, F. and S.U. Guan (2011), Tree-structure based ontology integration, *Journal of Information Science*, Vol. 37, pp. 594-613.

Xu, P, Wang, Y and B. Liu (2012), A differentor-based adaptive ontology-matching approach. *Journal of Information Science*, Vol. 38, pp. 459-475.

Zeginis, D., Tzitzikas, Y. and V. Christophides (2011), On computing deltas of RDF/S knowledge bases, *ACM Transactions on the Web (TWEB)*, Vol. 5 No. 3, pp. 1-36.